

Supplementary Figure S1. UHPLC-HRMS/MS Orbitrap total ion chromatogram (TIC) of the *n*-hexane extract of *O. onur-koyuncui* seeds. The annotated compounds were identified using retention times (RT), accurate mass measurements, authentic reference standards, and MS/MS fragmentation patterns.

Supplementary Figure S2. UHPLC-HRMS/MS Orbitrap total ion chromatogram (TIC) of the 70% aqueous methanol extract of *O. onur-koyuncui* seeds. The annotated compounds were identified using retention times (RT), accurate mass measurements, authentic reference standards, and MS/MS fragmentation patterns.

Supplementary Figure S3. UHPLC-HRMS/MS Orbitrap extracted ion chromatograms (EICs) and corresponding MS² spectra of the phenolic compounds identified in the *n*-hexane extract of *O. onur-koyuncui* seeds. Compound annotations were supported by retention times (RT), precursor ions, accurate mass measurements, and MS/MS fragmentation patterns. The chromatograms and spectra include RT, precursor-ion, and fragment-ion information supporting compound annotation and correspond to the compounds listed in Table 6.

Compound	MS/MS spectrum	Extracted ion chromatogram
Epicatechin	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_1_Epicatequina #: 1876 RT: 4.33 NL: 1.26E+08 F: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [50.0000-750.0000]</p>	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_1_Epicatequina RT: 4.33 AA: 2374130 AH: 1075448 NL: 1.03E6 m/z: 289.07178</p>
Taxifolin	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_1_Taxifolina #: 2162 RT: 5.01 NL: 1.23E+08 F: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [50.0000-750.0000]</p>	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_1_Taxifolina RT: 5.01 AA: 96366 AH: 46265 NL: 6.02E6 m/z: 383.05103</p>
Quercetin	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_2_Quercetina #: 2871 RT: 6.65 NL: 1.32E+08 F: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [50.0000-750.0000]</p>	<p>250206_KO3M_top6neg_2_Quercetina RT: 6.65 MA: 15189 MH: 18575 NL: 1.07E6 m/z: 361.03238</p>

Naringenin

Diosmetin

Supplementary Figure S4. UHPLC-HRMS/MS Orbitrap extracted ion chromatograms (EICs) and corresponding MS² spectra of the phenolic compounds identified in the 70% aqueous methanol extract of *O. onur-koyuncui* seeds. The chromatograms and spectra provide RT, precursor-ion, and fragment-ion information supporting compound identification. The chromatograms and spectra include RT, precursor-ion, and fragment-ion information supporting compound annotation and correspond to the compounds listed in Table 7.

Caffeic acid

p-Coumaric acid

Taxifolin

Naringin

Salicylic acid

Eriodictyol

Abscisic acid

Quercetin

Naringenin

Diosmetin

Supplementary Table S5. Calibration curve parameters, regression equations, and coefficients of determination (R^2) of phenolic reference standards used for UHPLC-HRMS/MS quantitative determination of the compounds identified in Table 6 and Table 7.

No	Compound	Linear range (ng/mL)	Regression equation	R^2
1	4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=2.0116 \times 10^5 X+2.1396$	0.9985
2	4-O-Caffeoylquinic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=5.7426 \times 10^4 X+1.865 \times 10^6$	0.9935
3	Apigenin-7-O-glucoside	4.883–5000	$Y=4.0824 \times 10^4 X+7.4426 \times 10^5$	0.9960
4	3-Hydroxytyrosol	0.488–500	$Y=1.8916 \times 10^5 X+3.196$	0.9991
5	Catechin	0.488–500	$Y=6.1426 \times 10^4 X+6.5416$	0.9973
6	Epicatechin	4.883–5000	$Y=7.9836 \times 10^4 X-1.5276 \times 10^5$	0.9985
7	Abcisic acid	0.488–500	$Y=2.8126 \times 10^5 X+1.0196 \times 10^5$	0.9999
8	Caffeic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=4.3476 \times 10^4 X+2.5786 \times 10^4$	0.9994
9	Chlorogenic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=5.3366 \times 10^4 X+1.0936 \times 10^4$	0.9977
10	Gentisic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=1.2165 \times 10^5 X+5.8024$	0.9990
11	Homovanillic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=7.4866 \times 10^3 X-4.2146 \times 10^5$	0.9929
12	<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	4.883–5000	$Y=3.9165 \times 10^5 X+4.615 \times 10^5$	0.9995
13	Protocatechuic acid	2.93–3000	$Y=2.4426 \times 10^5 X+3.81265$	0.9995
14	Diosmetin	4.883–5000	$Y=1.9776 \times 10^4 X-1.0716 \times 10^5$	0.9975
15	Eriodictyol	4.883–5000	$Y=1.6936 \times 10^5 X+2.6746 \times 10^5$	0.9986
16	Flavanomarein	4.883–5000	$Y=1.8596 \times 10^4 X+1.4385 \times 10^5$	0.9981
17	Quercetin	4.883–5000	$Y=2.0356 \times 10^5 X+3.3464 \times 10^4$	0.9989
18	Salicylic acid	4.883–5000	$Y=8.5046 \times 10^5 X+2.1346 \times 10^6$	0.9997
19	Hesperidin	4.883–5000	$Y=9.3146 \times 10^3 X+5.6986 \times 10^5$	0.9952
20	Isorhamnetin	4.883–5000	$Y=8.7626 \times 10^4 X+5.7446 \times 10^5$	0.9983
21	Morin	4.883–5000	$Y=3.9876 \times 10^4 X-5.986 \times 10^5$	0.9991
22	Luteolin	4.883–5000	$Y=2.2516 \times 10^5 X+6.329 \times 10^5$	0.9938
23	Naringenin	4.883–5000	$Y=2.4746 \times 10^5 X+1.858 \times 10^6$	0.9986
24	Naringin	0.488–500	$Y=2.7096 \times 10^4 X+1.5964 \times 10^4$	0.9926
25	Vanillin	4.883–5000	$Y=3.5776 \times 10^4 X+2.9086 \times 10^5$	0.9959
26	Taxifolin	4.883–5000	$Y=5.0056 \times 10^4 X+4.5686 \times 10^5$	0.9970

All compounds listed in this table were quantified using external calibration curves constructed from authentic reference standards.